

Optimal operation and analysis of a district heating supplier's portfolio: The Swedish case

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Abstract

This paper develops a mixed integer linear program (MILP) for optimal operation modelling and analysis of a district heating supplier's portfolio. The model aims to meet the heat demand with the lowest possible dispatch cost, while maximizing the profit from electricity trading in competitive day-ahead (DA) and manual frequency restorations reserves (mFRR) regulation markets. The proposed price driven MILP model is applied on a real system of a Swedish district heating (DH) company, namely Tekniska verken i Linköping AB (TvAB), to analyse the operation of TvAB's portfolio and the resulting participation in DA and mFRR markets. It is seen that an optimal operation of the portfolio while trading in the DA market alone results in a profit of about 156 MSEK, while also considering participation in mFRR markets in addition to DA increases the profit by another 2.75 MSEK.

Keywords: Sector-Coupling, Two-settlement Market, Optimal Scheduling, District Heating Supplier.

NOMENCLATURE

Indices

g	Generation unit
k	Storage unit
l	Startup type
m	Operation mode of CHP units; heat-only mode ($m=0$), full CHP mode ($m=1$)
p	Aggregated CHP unit
s	Segment defining PQ region of CHP units
t	Hour in optimization horizon, $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$

Parameters

η_g	Total efficiency of unit g (p.u.)
λ_t^{DA}	Day-ahead market price at time t (SEK/MWh)
$\lambda_t^{\text{up/dn}}$	Up or down-regulation market price at time t (SEK/MWh)
ω_1, ω_2	Penalties considered for heat dissipated and heat unserved (SEK/MWh)
ρ	Hourly loss rate for storage units (p.u.)
C^{CO_2}	Carbon tax per ton of emission (SEK/ton)
C_g^{fuel}	Fuel cost of unit g (SEK/MWh)
$C_{g,l}^{\text{S}}$	Startup cost of unit g for startup type l (SEK/start)
ER_g	Emission rate of unit g (ton/MWh)
H_t	System Heat Demand at time t (MW)
M_g^{max}	Maximum thermal (combined heat and electricity production) capacity of unit g (MW)
M_g^{min}	Minimum thermal (combined heat and electricity production) capacity of unit g (MW)
P_t^{self}	Internal electricity consumption at time t (MW)
$Q_{\text{HD}}^{\text{max}}$	Maximum capacity of heat sink (MW)
$q_{s,i}, p_{s,i}$	Endpoints of PQ segment s for aggregated CHP units (MWth, MWe)
t_p^{HO}	Minimum time in heat-only mode of unit p (hours)

$V_k^{\text{ch/dch}}$	Maximum charge/discharge rate of storage unit k (MW/h)
$V_k^{\text{max/min}}$	Maximum/minimum level of heat in storage unit k (MWh)

Variables

$\delta_{g,l,t}$	Continuous variable [0,1] for startup type l of unit g at time t
$F_{g,t}$	Fuel consumption of unit g at time t (MWh)
$M_{p,m,t}$	Binary variable for operation mode of aggregated CHP unit p
$N_{g,t}$	Total thermal power output, also considering startup and shutdown ramps, from unit g at time t (MW)
P_t^{DA}	Electricity sold in DA market at time t (MW)
$P_t^{\text{up/dn}}$	Electricity sold/bought in mFRR market at time t (MW)
$P_{g,t}$	Power production from unit g at time t (MW)
$P_{g,t}^{\text{up/dn}}$	Up/down regulation volume from unit g at time t (MW)
$P_{p,m,t}$	Power production from aggregated CHP unit p in mode m at time t (MW)
Q_t^{HD}	Heat dissipation at time t (MW)
Q_t^{uns}	Unserved heat demand at time t (MW)
$Q_{g,t}$	Heat production from unit g at time t (MW)
$Q_{p,m,t}$	Heat production from aggregated CHP unit p in mode m at time t (MW)
$R_{g,t}$	Total heat and power production from unit g at time t (MW)
$r_{g,t}$	Total (heat and power) output above minimum level from unit g at time t (MW)
$U_{g,t}$	Binary variable for on/off (unit-commitment) status of unit g at time t
$V_{k,t}$	Heat stored in storage unit k at time t (MWh)

1 Introduction

In present times, energy systems are undergoing a paradigm shift triggered by a global consensus for sustainable and environmentally friendly operation of the energy supply chain. The energy transition is a pathway towards transformation of the global energy sector from fossil-based to zero-carbon by 2050 [1]. In this context, some of the major challenges for electric power systems in years to come include the large-scale integration of renewable energy sources (RES), mobilization of demand response (DR), optimal investment in a risky environment, and the design of markets that provide appropriate operation and investment incentives.

Increasing and optimizing synergies between electricity, gas and heat systems helps in achieving higher flexibility, security of supply and a more economical operation for systems undergoing decarbonization. District heating (DH) is one such source of flexibility that can be integrated with power systems through different production units such as combined heat and power plants (CHPs), characterized by the cogeneration of heat and electric power, and heat pumps or electric boilers that produce heat from electricity. A DH supplier can follow electricity market price variations and provide flexibility to the power system by increasing or decreasing electricity production, also earning extra profits in this process. For example, during times of power excess in the grid, electricity production from CHP units can be decreased while the heating demand can be satisfied by using stored heat. For the case of deficit of electric power in the grid, the electricity production can be increased in the CHP units and the resulting heat production in excess of the heat demand can be stored instead.

Numerous previous works have dealt with the coupling between DH and power systems. Reference [2] performs an extensive review on the flexibility potential of DH systems and their ability to participate in various electricity markets. However, the recent study in [3] identifies that in Sweden, the utilization of DH systems for providing flexibility to the power system is very limited, owing to challenges with respect to legislation, incentives, ownership, etc. In this regard, it becomes interesting to develop a detailed mathematical model that evaluates the potential profitability of participating in one or more electricity markets for district heating suppliers. This study analyzes the application of such a model to a real system of a DH company (TvAB) in Sweden. The operation of different types of production units such as CHPs, heat boilers, flue gas condensation units and thermal storage is modelled, and the model addresses limitations in the actual feasibility of the DH units and the preferred practice of TvAB in providing balancing power in the mFRR market in Sweden.

2 Model Formulation

2.1 Objective function

The objective function given by (1) minimizes total operating costs of all units, which consist of fuel, startup and emission costs, while maximizing the revenue from electricity trading in the DA and mFRR markets. The terms $\lambda_t^{\text{up}} P_t^{\text{up}}$ and $\lambda_t^{\text{dn}} P_t^{\text{dn}}$

represent the compensation received from providing up and down regulation respectively. For the case when the portfolio participates only in the DA market, these two terms are not included in the objective function. Besides, penalty costs are included for the heat not served and heat dissipated. The excess heat dissipated is also penalized due to a lack of reliable cooling capacity in the system.

$$\min \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_g \left(C_g^{\text{fuel}} F_{g,t} + \sum_l C_{g,l}^S \delta_{g,l,t} + C^{\text{CO}_2} E R_g R_{g,t} \right) + \omega_1 Q_t^{\text{HD}} + \omega_2 Q_t^{\text{uns}} - \lambda_t^{\text{DA}} P_t^{\text{DA}} - \lambda_t^{\text{up}} P_t^{\text{up}} + \lambda_t^{\text{dn}} P_t^{\text{dn}} \right) \quad (1)$$

2.2 Constraints

Equation (2) ensures the heat balance in the system, while constraints (3) - (6) enforce other required limits on heat dissipated, not served or stored.

$$\sum_k (V_{k,t} - (1 - \rho) V_{k,t-1}) = \sum_g Q_{g,t} - (H_t - Q_t^{\text{uns}}) - Q_t^{\text{HD}} \quad (2)$$

$$Q_t^{\text{HD}} \leq Q_{HD}^{\text{max}} \quad (3)$$

$$Q_t^{\text{uns}} \leq H_t \quad (4)$$

$$V_k^{\text{min}} \leq V_{k,t} \leq V_k^{\text{max}} \quad (5)$$

$$-V_k^{\text{dch}} \leq V_{k,t} - V_{k,t-1} \leq V_k^{\text{ch}} \quad (6)$$

For condensation units, the power production is zero (7), while the heat production is proportional to the total output of the CHP units connected to them (8); this makes the total production equal to the heat production (9). Also, note that there is no fuel consumption associated with these units.

$$P_{g,t} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{g,t} \leq M_g^{\text{max}} \frac{\sum_j \text{connected to } g R_{j,t}}{\sum_j \text{connected to } g M_j^{\text{max}}} \quad (8)$$

$$R_{g,t} = Q_{g,t} \quad (9)$$

Constraints (10)-(18) are used to the model the operation of CHP units, based on [4],[5]. In many instances, two or more CHP units have a common steam stem from the boilers to the turbine, so we consider them as part of an aggregated CHP unit p with a common PQ region. In such a case, the total power and heat production from the aggregated unit are given by (10) and (11). However, for consistency in the formulation, single CHP units with own PQ region are also modelled as belonging to an aggregated unit p , that contains only one CHP unit nevertheless. Also, CHP units can operate in either CHP mode, producing both power and heat, or in heat boiler mode, producing only heat. Operation in either modes is modelled using the binary variables $M_{p,m,t}$, such that $m = 0$ represents the heat-only mode, while $m = 1$ corresponds to the CHP mode. Constraints (12) and (13) represent CHP operation in a convex region where $(q_{s,1}, p_{s,1})$ and $(q_{s,2}, p_{s,2})$ are the end-points of a line segment s of the convex region. Constraint

(14), along with (12) and (13) ensures that the power and heat production in CHP mode is zero when the CHP mode is not active ($M_{p,1,t} = 0$). Constraint (17) relates the operating mode of the aggregated unit to the unit-commitment status; here $U_{g,t}$ corresponds to the unit-commitment of the individual CHP unit belonging to p with the lowest marginal cost. Finally, constraint (18) enforces a minimum time that the unit must operate in the heat-only mode (before switching to CHP mode if required), and the condition that only one among the two modes is active at any given time.

$$P_{p,1,t} = \sum_{\substack{g \in p \\ \& \text{ } g \text{ is CHP}}} P_{g,t} \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{p,0,t} + Q_{p,1,t} = \sum_{\substack{g \in p \\ \& \text{ } g \text{ is CHP}}} Q_{g,t} \quad (11)$$

For all segments s ,

If $q_{s,2} \geq q_{s,1}$,

$$P_{p,1,t} \geq \frac{p_{s,2} - p_{s,1}}{q_{s,2} - q_{s,1}} (Q_{p,1,t} - q_{s,1} M_{p,1,t}) + p_{s,1} M_{p,1,t} \quad (12)$$

If $q_{s,2} \leq q_{s,1}$,

$$P_{p,1,t} \leq \frac{p_{s,2} - p_{s,1}}{q_{s,2} - q_{s,1}} (Q_{p,1,t} - q_{s,1} M_{p,1,t}) + p_{s,1} M_{p,1,t} \quad (13)$$

$$P_{p,1,t} \leq \left(\max_s p_{s,j} \right) M_{p,1,t} \quad (14)$$

$$M_g^{\min} M_{p,0,t} \leq Q_{p,0,t} \leq M_g^{\max} M_{p,0,t} \quad (15)$$

$$P_{p,0,t} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$M_{p,1,t} + M_{p,0,t} = U_{g,t} \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=t}^{\min(T, t+t_p^{\text{HO}}-1)} (M_{p,1,\tau} + M_{p,0,t} - 1) \leq 0 \quad (18)$$

Additionally, for heat boilers and CHP units, the modelling of startup and shutdown processes, including different startup types is based on [6], which also includes the customary constraints for production limits, unit-commitment, initial conditions, etc. As a result, the formulation for the same is not repeated here. However, it is important to note that since we consider a cogeneration system in our study, all variables corresponding to electric power in [6] equivalently represent the total, i.e., both electric and heat power in our case. Specifically, variables $r_{g,t}$ and $N_{g,t}$ in our formulation are equivalent in this sense to variables p_t and P_t in [6] respectively. Additional constraint (19) then divides the total output of the unit into power and heat components when committed. Also, while fuel consumption is dependent on the total production from the unit and its efficiency (20), constraints (21) and (22) define other quantities for heat boilers and CHP units.

$$r_{g,t} + M_g^{\min} U_{g,t} = P_{g,t} + Q_{g,t} \quad (19)$$

$$F_{g,t} = N_{g,t} / \eta_g \quad (20)$$

$$P_{g,t} = 0, R_{g,t} = Q_{g,t} \quad (\text{heat boiler}) \quad (21)$$

$$R_{g,t} = P_{g,t} + Q_{g,t} \quad (\text{CHP}) \quad (22)$$

Finally, the volume traded when participating in only the DA market is given by (23), where the power production from all units, after providing for the self-consumption by the system is traded on the DA market.

$$\sum_g P_{g,t} = P_t^{\text{DA}} + P_t^{\text{self}} \quad (23)$$

Constraints (24) - (34) are required when also considering participation in the mFRR market. Here, the power output of every unit g is broken up into components corresponding to the volumes traded on the DA and mFRR markets (24). Then, the total volumes from the portfolio that are traded on these markets are given by (25) - (27). While constraints (28) and (29) ensure that both up and down regulation cannot be provided at the same time and during hours when no regulation is needed (based on both DA and mFRR prices), constraint (30) enables a unit to provide down-regulation only when the down-regulating price, which is the cost of buying back production, is lower than the fuel or production cost of the unit. Additionally, constraint (31) limits the down-regulation that can be provided by the DA volume. Constraints (32) and (33) are used to enforce limits on the up and down regulation volumes that can be provided, depending on the actual regulation capability of the units within the required activation time. Here, we have assumed symmetrical capabilities for both up and down regulation. Finally, constraint (34) is required to ensure that up or down regulation can be provided by a unit only when it is committed; otherwise the terms $P_{g,t}^{\text{DA}}$ and $P_{g,t}^{\text{dn}}$ may take non-zero values without the unit being committed to cancel each other in the constraint (24).

$$P_{g,t} = P_{g,t}^{\text{DA}} + P_{g,t}^{\text{up}} - P_{g,t}^{\text{dn}} \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_g P_{g,t}^{\text{DA}} = P_t^{\text{DA}} + P_t^{\text{self}} \quad (25)$$

$$\sum_g P_{g,t}^{\text{up}} = P_t^{\text{up}} \quad (26)$$

$$\sum_g P_{g,t}^{\text{dn}} = P_t^{\text{dn}} \quad (27)$$

$$P_{g,t}^{\text{up}} = 0, \text{ if } \lambda_t^{\text{DA}} \geq \lambda_t^{\text{up}} \quad (28)$$

$$P_{g,t}^{\text{dn}} = 0, \text{ if } \lambda_t^{\text{DA}} \leq \lambda_t^{\text{dn}} \quad (29)$$

$$P_{g,t}^{\text{dn}} = 0, \text{ if } \lambda_t^{\text{dn}} \geq C_g^{\text{fuel}} \quad (30)$$

$$P_t^{\text{dn}} \leq P_t^{\text{spot}} \quad (31)$$

$$P_{g,t}^{\text{up}} \leq \overline{P_{\text{mFRR}}}_g \quad (32)$$

$$P_{g,t}^{\text{dn}} \leq \overline{P_{\text{mFRR}}}_g \quad (33)$$

$$P_{g,t}^{\text{DA}} + P_{g,t}^{\text{up}} \leq \left(\max_s p_{s,j} \right) U_{g,t} \quad (34)$$

3 Case Study

TvAB's production portfolio comprises six CHP units, four flue gas condensation (FGC) units, three heat-only boilers (HB) and a heat storage. The CHP units belong to two main CHP plants, namely 'Kraftvärmeverket' (referred to as 'KV1') and 'Gärstadverket', which is a waste-incineration plant (denoted as WP). Production related data and parameters for

all units in the portfolio are received through communication with TvAB; a significant part of this data is summarized in table 1. For the waste plant, the total marginal cost is considered to be practically zero, as the income TvAB receives for the waste treatment cancels the costs it faces with processing the waste and the costs arising from carbon emissions due to waste incineration. Hence, in the implementation, we do not have a separate term for emissions in the objective function for the waste plant; the emissions from the waste plant are calculated instead from the final optimization solution, considering an emission rate of 0.2 ton/MWh. Also, apart from the waste plant, only the heat boilers that are oil-based (HB 1 and 2) result in emissions amounting to 0.5 and 0.4 ton/MWh respectively.

With regard to other operational considerations, startups are considered for all units except flue gas condensers and are assumed to be cold starts, corresponding to a startup cost and duration. Also, while a shutdown time of one hour is assumed for all units, the associated shutdown cost is zero. Up and down ramping limits, over a one hour interval, apply only to CHP 2 of KV1 plant at 90 MW/h. Heat and power production of the CHP units, when operating in CHP mode, are constrained to respect a simple linear relationship, instead of a convex feasible region. When in heat-only mode, we impose a minimum operation time of 2 hours before the unit can switch to the CHP mode, if needed. Besides, TvAB also has a heat storage with a capacity of 2.5 GWh. Maximum charge/dishcharge rates are 150 MW/h, while hourly losses from the storage are considered to be insignificant. Internal power consumption in TvAB's system is about 6 MW and 10 MW hourly during summer and winter respectively. The total capacity of heat sinks, which mainly consists of the local river, is 50 MW. However, since the heat absorbing capacity of the river is very unreliable due to low precipitation during most of the year, we impose high penalty costs for heat discharge, as previously given in the objective function 1.

Hourly heat demand of the Linköping DH system is received from TvAB, for the reference year of interest (2021). Figure 1 illustrates the same with a daily resolution. Since the city of Linköping is located in bidding zone SE3 in Sweden, we obtain the DA and mFRR market prices for zone SE3 for 2021 from the ENTSO-E transparency platform [7]. Besides, to participate in the mFRR market in Sweden, the balancing service provider must be able to activate 100% of the offered regulating capacity within 15 minutes. Considering this requirement, TvAB prefers to have only the KV1 CHP plant to provide regulation; the waste plant with lowest marginal cost is assumed to cover the base heat demand in the system and not contribute to regulation capacity. Moreover, the regulation capacity of even the KV1 CHP units is limited, at about 15 MW steam output in 15 minutes. We incorporate these practical limitations for the case of the DH portfolio participating in both DA and mFRR markets.

4 Results

The mathematical models were coded in Python/Pyomo and run using the CPLEX solver on a PC with 64 GB RAM and In-

tel(R) Core(TM) i7-10700K CPU. Due to computational and time limitations, these models were solved with a duality gap of 10%. Enhancing the models' tractability with better formulations are part of planned future work, but it can also be noted that these models have been run for an optimization horizon of an entire year with hourly resolution, considering the need to capture the impact of hourly variability in market prices.

Figure 1: TvAB daily heat demand in 2021.

Figure 2: Power production dispatch - DA market

Figure 3: Heat production dispatch - DA market

Figure 4: Power Trading - DA and mFRR markets

From figure 1, we see that the heat demand is higher in the winter months and relatively lower in the summer months.

Table 1: TvAB Unit Data

Unit	Type	Fuel	Fuel Cost (SEK/MWh)	Thermal Capacities (MW) Max/Min	Power- Heat Ratio	Efficiency (p.u.)	Startup Time (h)	Startup Cost (SEK/start)	Minimum Up/Dn Hours
1	CHP 1 - KV1	Recycled Wood	350	60/30	0.31	0.8	24	250k	72/72
2	CHP 2 - KV1	Bio-oil	2000	120/30	0.31	0.8	8	250k	2/12
3	CHP 3 - KV1	Recycled Wood	290	60/30	0.31	0.8	24	250k	72/72
4	CHP 1 - WP	Waste	0	75/20	0.15	0.9	24	250k	72/72
5	CHP 2 - WP	Waste	0	66/44	0.29	0.9	24	250k	72/72
6	CHP 3 - WP	Waste	0	83/55	0.34	0.9	24	250k	72/72
7	FGC 1 - Unit 3	-	0	13/0	-	-	-	-	-
8	FGC 2 - Unit 4	-	0	10/0	-	-	-	-	-
9	FGC 3 - Unit 5	-	0	14/0	-	-	-	-	-
10	FGC 4 - Unit 6	-	0	10/0	-	-	-	-	-
11	HB 1	Oil	2500	45/10	-	0.9	4	250k	2/12
12	HB 2	Oil	2500	40/10	-	0.9	4	250k	2/12
13	HB 3	Bio-oil	2000	40/10	-	0.9	4	250k	2/12

Power and heat production dispatch, for the case when the portfolio participates only in the DA market, are presented in figures 2 and 3, while figure 4 shows the traded volumes by the portfolio for both cases of participating in only DA and both DA and mFRR markets. The figures illustrate that during the summer months when both the heat demand and market prices are low, only two units of waste plant are committed to meet the heat demand. However, the model behaviour is different during the winter months when the heat demand is high. The model dispatches most of the units to meet the heat demand, combined with trading in electricity markets. Consequently, higher volumes are traded during winter months as seen in figure 4. It should be noted that the thermal storage is small and the DH system does not have reliable cooling capacity; as a result, CHP units of the KV1 plant become restricted from operating during times of low heat demand even if the market prices are favourable for trading more electricity. Table 2 summarizes the results for both cases; we see that trading possibility in both DA and mFRR markets generates lower dispatch cost and higher profit compared to participating in only the DA market.

Table 2: Dispatch and Economic Metrics

Metric	DA	DA and mFRR
Electric Power Dispatch (GWh)	372	352.33
Heat Power Dispatch (GWh)	1547	1547
Total Cost of Dispatch (MSEK)	102.5	92.98
Total Revenue (MSEK)	258.6	251.84
Total Profit (MSEK)	156.1	158.85

5 Conclusion

In this work, a MILP model has been developed for optimal operation of the production portfolio of a Swedish DH supplier, considering participation in the DA and mFRR markets. Different types of production units such as CHPs, heat boilers, flue gas condensation units and thermal storage are modelled, considering various operational constraints. The developed model can therefore support DH suppliers to estimate the profitability of participating in the specified electricity markets, while also enabling them to evaluate different options for increasing the profitability such as investing in cooling capacity, increasing the capacity of heat storage, and addressing the capability of CHP plants to provide more balancing power.

Acknowledgement

This work has been carried out as part of the BioFlexGen project, funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 LC-GD-2-1-2020 R&I Actions (<https://bioflexgen.eu/project/>).

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